

Do environmental amenities add a premium to property prices? Evidence from Bengaluru

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Summary

This study examines the influence of urban environmental quality on apartment prices in Bengaluru, India, utilizing spatial econometrics and interpretable machine learning. The Enhanced Vegetation Index (EVI), Normalized Difference Built-up Index (NDBI), and Land Surface Temperature (LST) were extracted from Landsat 8 and 9 imagery and linked to 4,665 housing transactions from 2024. Spatial diagnostics confirm significant spatial dependence, which is addressed using SAR and SEM models. To capture nonlinear effects, XGBoost models were applied and interpreted using SHAP values, revealing the strong local role of vegetation quality. The findings underscore the economic value of environmental conditions for sustainable urban development and policy, thereby contributing to achieving SDGs 11 and 13.

KEYWORDS: Housing prices, Urban environmental quality, Spatial econometrics, Machine Learning, Sustainable cities.

1 Introduction

Urban areas in developing and rapidly urbanising regions face increasing environmental stress from climate change and intensive land-use transformation. Among these challenges, the Urban Heat Island (UHI) effect has become a major concern, as rising land surface temperatures intensify public health risks, increase energy demand, and strain fragile urban ecosystems (Hao and Zheng, 2017). These impacts are socially uneven and closely linked to housing quality, access to green infrastructure, and governance disparities, reinforcing concerns around urban sustainability and environmental equity (Barton et al., 2021).

Housing markets provide a behavioural mechanism through which such environmental conditions can be evaluated. Property prices reflect households' revealed preferences for structural, locational, and ecological attributes, offering an empirical pathway to quantify the economic value of urban

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environmental quality. While conventional housing determinants are well documented (Bangura and Lee, 2023; Soltani et al., 2026), environmental dimensions remain fragmented in urban economic research. Many studies examine single indicators—such as green proximity or air quality—without capturing their combined spatial and thermal interactions (Wang and Lee, 2022; Soltani et al., 2023, 2026).

Reliance on vegetation quantity measures such as NDVI also overlooks qualitative aspects of green environments and residents’ lived experiences (Gren, 2008). At the same time, higher land surface temperatures are associated with lower housing values due to reduced thermal comfort and increased cooling costs (Soltani et al., 2026). However, these environmental dimensions are rarely examined together within a unified spatial framework.

Remote sensing indicators provide consistent measures of urban environmental conditions. Vegetation indices capture environmental quality and cooling effects, while built-up indices represent urban density and land-use intensity. Higher vegetation levels are generally associated with cooler temperatures, improved environmental quality, and higher property values, whereas greater built-up intensity often corresponds to higher heat exposure and reduced liveability (Ashwini and Sil, 2022; Vaddiraju and Reshma, 2022). These indicators therefore offer a practical way to capture vegetation quality, built-up intensity, and thermal exposure in housing market analysis.

This study makes three significant contributions to the literature. It moves beyond single-indicator representations of the urban environment by directly measuring vegetation quality (EVI), built-up intensity (NDBI), and thermal stress (LST) using remote sensing techniques. Second, it combines interpretable machine learning methods with spatial econometric models, enabling explicit identification of nonlinear responses and spatial dependence rather than relying on implicit assumptions. Third, it applies this framework to Bengaluru, India, a rapidly changing megacity in South Asia where pressures on housing affordability and environmental externalities are growing but have not yet been thoroughly studied empirically.

By doing this, the study clarifies which environmental amenity has the most significant impact on the overall experience. It provides policy-relevant evidence on how various aspects of urban environmental quality are reflected in housing prices. The analysis addresses two research questions: (1) Do LST, NDBI, and EVI have a significant influence on housing prices? and (2) Which of these environmental factors is most important in influencing price fluctuations?

2 Study Area & Data

This study examines Bengaluru, a rapidly urbanising metropolis in southern India that has experienced significant degradation of green and blue infrastructure. Historically known as the Garden City and the City of Lakes, Bengaluru once supported extensive vegetation and nearly 209 interconnected lakes that regulated local climate and hydrology (Ramachandra and Aithal, 2016). Accelerated urbanisation has since intensified land-use change and urban heat stress. The analysis is restricted to the Bruhat Bengaluru Mahanagara Palike (BBMP), the city’s core administrative area, covering approximately 709 km² across eight zones and 198 wards.

Figure 1: Distribution of the apartment sales data used in the analysis area

The dataset comprises 4,665 apartment transactions recorded between January and August 2024 within the BBMP boundary (see Fig. 1). Transaction-level data were obtained from Propstack¹, while neighbourhood and amenity variables were derived from OpenStreetMap. Environmental indicators— Enhanced Vegetation Index (EVI), Normalized Difference Built-up Index (NDBI), and Land Surface Temperature (LST)—were computed using Landsat 8 and Landsat 9 imagery. Monthly satellite observations were processed and averaged to represent environmental conditions during the study period. All ecological indicators were calculated within a 300 m buffer, approximating a five-minute walking distance, to capture residents’ immediate environmental exposure (Azmi et al., 2018). The dependent variable is the logarithm of apartment sale price, with explanatory variables capturing structural, locational, and ecological attributes.

¹<https://www.propstack.com/>

3 Methodology

This study employs a multi-stage analytical framework integrating hedonic pricing, spatial econometrics, and interpretable machine learning. First, a hedonic pricing model (HPM) estimates the implicit value of housing attributes, treating residential properties as bundles of structural, neighbourhood, and environmental characteristics (Rosen, 1974). Second, spatial diagnostics test for spatial dependence in housing prices. Third, spatial econometric models account for detected spatial effects. Finally, machine learning models explore nonlinear relationships and evaluate the relative importance of environmental variables using SHapley Additive exPlanations (SHAP).

3.1 Spatial Econometric Modelling

The hedonic price function is specified in log-linear form, widely used in housing market analysis for interpretability and to reduce heteroskedasticity (Elhorst, 2014). The baseline model is first estimated using Ordinary Least Squares (OLS):

$$p = \beta_0 + \sum_k \beta_k S_{ik} + \sum_j \beta_j L_{ij} + \varepsilon, \quad (1)$$

where p is the vector of housing prices, S_{ik} represents structural attributes, L_{ij} captures locational and environmental characteristics, and ε is a random error term. Housing prices exhibit spatial dependence because nearby properties tend to have similar values due to neighbourhood spillovers and unobserved local factors. Ignoring this dependence may lead to biased and inefficient OLS estimates. Spatial autocorrelation is tested using Global Moran's I and Lagrange Multiplier (LM) diagnostics.

Based on these tests, Spatial Autoregressive (SAR) and Spatial Error Models (SEM) are estimated (LeSage and Pace, 2009). The SAR model captures spatial spillovers through a spatially lagged dependent variable:

$$p = \beta_0 + \rho Wp + X\beta + \varepsilon, \quad (2)$$

where W is the spatial weight matrix defining neighbourhood structure, ρ captures price spillovers, and ε is an independently distributed error term. Alternatively, spatial dependence arising from omitted or latent spatial processes is addressed using the SEM:

$$p = \beta_0 + X\beta + u, \quad (3)$$

$$u = \lambda Wu + \varepsilon, \quad (4)$$

where λ captures spatial autocorrelation in the error structure and ε is the uncorrelated error term. Unlike SAR, SEM corrects spatial dependence without implying price spillovers across locations (Anselin, 1988; Elhorst, 2014). Standardized coefficients are reported for comparability.

3.2 Machine Learning for Nonlinear Effects

Machine learning models capture nonlinear relationships and complex interactions. Support Vector Regression (SVR) (Smola and Schölkopf, 2004) is used as a nonlinear benchmark, while XGBoost (Chen, 2016) serves as the primary predictive model. Interpretability is ensured using SHapley Additive exPlanations (SHAP) (Lundberg and Lee, 2017). Machine learning complements, rather than replaces, econometric inference.

4 Results

The baseline OLS hedonic model explains approximately 25% of the variation in housing prices and identifies several significant structural, locational, and environmental determinants. Built-up area shows a strong positive association with housing prices, confirming the dominant role of dwelling size. Accessibility variables, including proximity to parks, railway stations, and technology hubs, also show positive effects, highlighting the importance of urban amenities and employment access. Among environmental variables, vegetation quality (EVI) has a positive and statistically significant effect, indicating that greener neighbourhoods command price premiums. Built-up intensity (NDBI) is statistically insignificant, while land surface temperature (LST) shows a weak negative association, suggesting limited explanatory power in a linear specification.

Residual diagnostics reveal substantial spatial dependence. The Global Moran’s I statistic equals 0.2782 ($p < 0.001$), indicating strong spatial clustering in housing prices beyond observed covariates. This suggests that OLS fails to capture spatial spillovers and unobserved neighbourhood effects, motivating the use of spatial econometric models.

The Spatial Error Model (SEM) reveals strong and significant spatial autocorrelation in the error term ($\lambda = 0.580$, $p < 0.001$), indicating that latent neighbourhood-level factors drive spatial dependence. After controlling for this dependence, vegetation quality (EVI) remains positive and significant, confirming its robustness as an environmental amenity. NDBI remains insignificant, while the LST effect weakens further, suggesting that thermal impacts on housing prices may be nonlinear or context-specific. Results from the Spatial Autoregressive (SAR) model show a significant spatial lag coefficient, indicating price spillovers across neighbouring properties. Together, these findings highlight the importance of accounting for spatial processes when estimating environmental effects on housing prices (see Table 1).

Machine learning models substantially improve predictive performance, indicating nonlinear relationships and complex interactions. The SVR model achieves an out-of-sample R^2 of 0.48 (RMSE = 0.38), while XGBoost performs best with an R^2 of 0.61 (RMSE = 0.33). Permutation-based feature importance from the SVR model identifies built-up area as the dominant predictor, followed by financial facilities, built-up intensity (NDBI), medical facilities, and land surface temperature. In contrast, SHAP analysis of the XGBoost model indicates that vegetation quality (EVI) is a more influential environmental factor than NDBI, with higher EVI values increasing housing prices. This divergence reflects methodological differences: SVR captures global sensitivity, whereas SHAP reveals localized nonlinear effects. Overall, urban density shapes overall price levels, while high-quality green environments differentiate housing values at the neighbourhood scale (see Fig. 2).

Table 1: Hedonic, Spatial Error, and Spatial Lag Regression Results

Variable	Description	OLS	SEM	SAR
Intercept	Constant term	13.159***	13.037***	4.660***
Log Area	Log of built-up area	0.492***	0.482***	0.437***
Floor Level	Floor of apartment	0.00001**	0.00001*	0.00001*
Sale Type	Encoded sale type	-0.087***	-0.087***	-0.070***
Bus Stops (1 km)	Bus stop density	-0.001	0.00019	-0.002
Financial Facilities (1 km)	Banks & ATMs density	0.009***	0.005**	0.004***
Medical Facilities (1 km)	Clinics & hospitals	-0.004**	-0.003	-0.001
Distance to Metro	Distance to nearest metro station(m)	0.000	0.000	0.000
Distance to Railway	Distance to nearest railway station(m)	-0.000***	-0.00002	-0.00001**
Schools (1 km)	School density	-0.009***	-0.002	-0.004**
Kindergartens (1 km)	Childcare density	0.009**	0.006	0.002
Distance to Supermarket	Distance to nearest supermarket(m)	0.00001	-0.00003	0.00001
Distance to Tech Hub	Distance to nearest IT cluster(m)	-0.00003***	-0.00003**	-0.00001**
Distance to Park	Distance to nearest park(m)	-0.00030***	-0.00029***	-0.00018***
Vegetation Quality (EVI)	Enhanced Vegetation Index (300 m)	1.583***	1.219**	0.874**
Built-up Intensity (NDBI)	Built density index (300 m)	0.094	-0.070	-0.000
Land Surface Temperature	LST (300 m)	-0.023**	-0.018	-0.008
Spatial Lag (W×Price)		–	–	0.525***
Spatial Error (λ)		–	0.580***	–
R^2 / Pseudo- R^2		0.251	0.247	0.393
AIC		6081.9	5210.4	5286.2

Notes: *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.10$.

5 Conclusion

This study demonstrates that a reliable and scalable framework for examining how environmental quality is capitalised into urban housing markets can be developed by combining spatial econometric and interpretable machine learning techniques with GIS-derived ecological indicators. The analysis moves beyond traditional single-indicator approaches by capturing spatial dependence and nonlinear valuation effects through the integration of remote sensing data, hedonic modelling, and machine learning.

Vegetation quality emerges as a consistent environmental determinant of housing values across both econometric and machine learning models. Even after accounting for structural, locational, and spatial spillover effects, the positive and significant influence of the enhanced vegetation index (EVI) indicates that households place a measurable premium on high-quality green environments. In contrast, built-up intensity shapes overall price levels rather than differentiating values at the neighbourhood scale, reflecting its more structural and context-dependent role. This difference is evident in the divergence between SVR and XGBoost interpretations: while SVR captures global sensitivity to urban density, XGBoost combined with SHAP reveals localised and nonlinear valuation effects associated with vegetation quality.

The findings also suggest that land surface temperature, representing thermal conditions, has more complex and context-specific effects on housing prices. These effects are better captured through

Figure 2: Comparison of machine learning model interpretations: permutation-based global feature importance from the SVR model (left) and SHAP-based local and nonlinear feature contributions from the XGBoost model (right).

flexible modelling techniques than through linear specifications alone. This highlights the importance of integrating machine learning with spatial econometrics rather than treating them as competing approaches.

The results are relevant to Sustainable Development Goal 11, indicating that accessible, high-quality green infrastructure generates economic benefits for inclusive and liveable cities. They also contribute to Sustainable Development Goal 13 by highlighting the relationship between vegetation quality and thermal environmental conditions in shaping residential desirability under increasing urban heat stress. The use of remotely sensed environmental metrics as an operational tool in housing market analysis provides spatially explicit evidence that urban planners and policymakers can use to support climate-sensitive green initiatives aimed at improving ecological resilience and social well-being in rapidly urbanising regions of the Global South.

6 Biography

Sayan Roy is a PhD researcher in the Department of Management Studies at the Indian Institute of Science (IISc), Bengaluru, specialising in urban economics, spatial analysis, and GIS-based environmental assessment. His research integrates remote sensing, spatial econometrics, and machine learning to support sustainable urban planning in rapidly urbanising Indian cities.

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